

Dalit Women and Higher Education on Rural Areas in Dindigul District of Tamil Nadu

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M. Vaishnavi

UGC-RGNF Fellow & FT Ph.D. Research Scholar

Dr.S.Xavier, Ph.D.,

Assistant Professor, Department of History

Periyar EVR College (Autonomous), Tiruchirappalli – 620 023, Tamil Nadu

Abstract

Ensuring access to education for the Dalits of India has been the greatest challenge for the Indian government in diminishing the social effects of the caste system, which still remain entrenched in Indian society. While India is one of the fastest-growing economies in the world, many rural villages and communities are suffering from a lack of Education opportunities. Less than half of all children in India's villages attend school. Approximately one third of village adults are illiterate. And social discrimination against people of "dalit" background (lower caste) results in limited opportunity to develop skills and capabilities. Bridge IT demonstrates the use of IT as an enabler in primary education and adult literacy and helps create digital entrepreneurs who help local citizens. The presence of computers in the classrooms improves attendance (up 52% in most schools); children want to participate, and parents see the value of learning computer skills. Tata Affirmative Action Program adopted by the Tata group in April 2007, which focuses on the Education, Employability, Employment and Entrepreneurship in the program attempts to address the prevailing social inequities in India by proactively reaching out to the Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribes (SC/ST) communities. There have been many different reasons proposed as to why the Dalits suffer from low rates of literacy and primary education enrolment, but the most realistic one describes history and unequal access as the causes. The ancient caste system of India, which has resulted in the social and economic oppression of the Dalits, continues to play a dominant role in India. Dalit education were coming from outside influences, rather than from the national government. Because of unchanging social norms and behaviour, incentives to pursue education were minimal for the Dalits who were still physically and emotionally harassed. Increasing efforts to eliminate caste discrimination combined with additional attempts to increase the accessibility and appeal for education have contributed to the slow progression of Dalit education. Recently the atrocities perpetrated by the dominant caste groups on Dalits is an indicator of the situation referred above and Dalits have learnt the language of protest and their assertion of rights which normally leads to caste tensions. Therefore, the atrocities on Dalits are the bubbles of caste tensions beneath the social system in rural India.

Introduction

Education for the Dalits of India has been the greatest challenge for the Indian government in diminishing the social effects of the caste

system, which still remain entrenched in Indian society. There have been many different reasons proposed as to why the Dalits suffer from low rates of literacy and primary education enrolment, but the most realistic one describes history and unequal access as the causes. The ancient caste system of India, which has resulted in the social and economic oppression of the Dalits, continues to play a dominant role in India. The Dalit population continues to struggle for equality, though the progress of the past few decades shows hope for an improved level of equality within Indian society.

Review of Literature

Barry (1998) argues that schools exclude if their selection policy results in children of a homogenous social background on the grounds that much research shows that “children with middle class attitudes and aspirations constitute a reforce for the rest”.

P. Sampath (2009) discusses that dalits in Madurai city were hunted by problems such as poor health and unhygienic living conditions. They also lacked proper housing, a proper environment for education, employments, finance assistance for self-employment and social mobility, and faced delays in the disbursement of welfare assistance, including old age pension. Non-issuance of pattas for those who have been residing in the city for more than three decades is another issue highlighted by the author.

Anand Teltumbde’s discussion on the impact of economic reforms on Dalits in India reveals that to be meaningful to the majority of India’s poor. Any reform strategy must embody sustainable economic empowerment of rural masses; investments to enhance their capability and effective measures for accelerated development of the disadvantaged sections like dalits. The pre-requisite to reforms therefore, could be the radical land reforms, massive investments in rural areas into agriculture related infrastructural projects, universalisation of primary education, primary health care system and reinforcement of positive discrimination in favour of dalits.

Points out that those countries going through economic that have invested in education are more likely to emerge with far less damage and much greater potential to rebound in the new market economy and the liberal state.

Statement of the problem: Education helps to ensure that benefits of growth are experienced by all. Economic perspectives see education as a means to make individuals more productive in the workplace and at home. It can also be seen as a means of empowering socially and economically deprived groups into seeking political reform. By using any of these reasons as motivation to pursue educational development, governments are attempting to generate some form of social or economic equality for the population. Providing primary education to 10% more people would equate to a decrease in the inequality index of 5% The economic advantages of increasing enrolment rates for primary education emphasize the importance of increasing education accessibility for the dalits of India. Education for all of India have been made, although the difference between education rates for Dalits, especially females, and those in higher castes remained constant. In the seventeen year period, enrolment rates for Dalit boys grew from only 47.7% to a meagre 63.25%. When compared to those males in upper castes, enrolments jumped from an already relatively impressive 73.22% to 82.92%. Even poorer results were observed when looking at the female Dalit enrolment rate, which inched from 15.72% to 32.61%, when compared to their upper-caste counterparts whose enrolment climbed from 43.56% to 59.15%. The education gap can also be understood to translate through the entire schooling system, with the proportion of Dalit to non-Dalit success remaining at a constant low rate through primary, secondary, and post-secondary schooling. Although large improvements have been made to increase enrolment rates in India, statistics show that there has been little progress in decreasing the education gap between castes.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the socio-economic background of the Dalit children.
2. To capture the coping strategies deployed by Dalit children to deal with school exclusion.
3. To analyse the causes and factors responsible for exclusion
4. To highlight the perception, aspirations and solutions regarding social exclusion faced by Dalit children.

Sample of the study: A total of 110 school-going Dalit children were included as respondents from the 10 villages sampled for the study. For the convenience of the research an average of 11 Dalit children from each of 10 villages were interviewed for this study.

Methodology: The purpose of the study is to study the prevalence and forms of the practice of discrimination and exclusion faced by School-going Dalit Children at school, by also recording in Arundhathiyar Children's own voice, the inner meanings and psychological interiority of them having to go through the experiences of subjugated and discriminated students at schools.

Tools for data collection : It is indeed very challenging to enter into the moral universe and the lifeworld of the subjects of the study, as it requires finest sensibilities and extraordinary sensitivity on the part of the researchers as well as appropriate research tools. Hence, this study relies heavily upon the application of qualitative research tools as well as the engagement with the field reality on a continuous and sustained basis. Accordingly the following research tools were deployed:

- Interview Schedule
- Group Interview
- Group Discussions
- Focused Group Discussions

Universe of the study: Universe of the study is comprised of all the Dalit students at the time of study in the selected village. The Dalit children constitute the universe of the study.

Primary data: Primary data were collected in face to face observation study and scale on the perspectives and problems of school going Dalit children.

Secondary data: The secondary data on this topic were collected through the relevant sources from books, journals, research articles, officials, reports, website, etc.

Nature of the study: Descriptive method has been adopted for this study.

Pilot study: Pilot study is a preliminary study to gain clear cut or specific knowledge in subject, undertake for a research study a pilot study is very essential. It simplifies the task of farming a scheduled and observation method.

Operational definition of the concepts used: A number of quantitative as well as qualitative variables used in in the present study have been operationalized in the following way.

Place of residence: Place of residence refers to the area of living of the Dalit respondents.

Education : Education is the formal education acquired by the Arunthathiyar respondents through formal educational institutions like school.

Profile of the Respondents

Age of the respondents

Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1-7	25	23
8-14	50	45
15-21	35	32
Total	110	100

For the study, the researcher has taken up a sample of 110 respondents. The ages-wise breakup is given above. From this table it is evident that there is an even breakup of age profile of the school-going children with those between the age group of 8-14 occupying exactly 50% of the total respondents. The next dominant age groups is that of 15-21, who occupies 35%.

Distribution of Respondents According To Gender

Sex	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	50	45
Female	60	55
Total	110	100

Of the total students sampled for the study, female students take up more shares in the total number of respondents selected for the study. From the table above it is clear that female students occupy majority in that they are 60%, whereas the male occupies 40%.

Educational Status of the Respondents

Educational status	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Primary	30	27
Secondary	65	59
High. Secondary	15	14
Total	110	100

When looking at the level of education of the respondents it is revealed that majority (65%) are at the secondary level. The second largest group is at the primary level, at which 30% are there. Higher secondary occupies only 15%.

Type of school

School nature	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Government	68	62
Government aided	30	27
Unaided	12	11
Total	110	100

The researcher has collected data about the type of school the students have been attending. The answer from the respondents reveal that a large majority (68%) of the students are attending classes at the government school, with the second largest group (30%) doing the same in government aided school. This is quite understandable since majority of the Dalit students are poor and cannot afford to study in private schools.

The availability of extra attention from school teacher for improving the performance of Dalit students

Degree	No. of villages	Percentage
High	2	20
Moderate	3	30
Nil	5	50
Total	10	100

The prevalence of freedom to choose their groups and subject of study

Degree	No. of villages	Percentage
High	2	20
Moderate	3	30
Nil	5	50
Total	10	100

In fact, other than just allowing them to school, no investment, either emotional or moral or financial is made in further improving the skills and talents of Dalit students. May be, the school authorities think that the very act of admission to school as so revolutionary and a big sacrifice, that no more importance must be given to further working on their welfare. Thus, Dalit children are not encouraged to take part in many extra-curricular activities, not sent for any cultural programmes, not given opportunities to improve their drawings, oratorical, singing musical skills.

Major Findings of the Study

- Even now in 80% of the selected villages Dalits are permitted only up to the backyard of the houses.
- In majority of the villages Dalits are deliberately discouraged from entering into Non- Dalits house, by offering only those chores performed outside the house, in the backyard.
- In almost all the villages Dalits are fed only outside the house structure in verandas, backyard, in cowsheds.
- In few villages Dalits are not even permitted to enter the Non-Dalits streets through the main street, they can enter via the back street.
- Most of the rich Non- Dalits houses are architecturally designed in such a manner that Dalits can enter and exit via separate path, and also a separate place in the backyard for feeding them after they finish the household chores demanded of them.
- In few villages, even today, Dalits have to remove their chappals or carry them as they go near the Non-Dalits house.
- Dalits women when going to work for cow-shed cleaning or other domestic chores, many of them carry their vessels to eat the food offered to them or they keep a separate vessel in the Non- Dalits houses where they go for regular work. The vessels are often old and used.

Suggestions

- The school teachers take tuition must and their needs to Dalit children.
- The teachers the motivated Dalit children and all the activities in particular education, sports and village festival time.
- The society should resolve not to discriminate Dalit children for this at school and college level there must be no discrimination day and please must be administered to that collect.
- At school levels caste-based alignment of student must be prohibited.
- To media get provide awareness training programmes and education programmes must be organised the TV channels.
- To promote government and NGOs to get providing loan for education and hostel, health, bus pass, etc.
- Dalit youth now depend upon others for economic and social well being. They must be free from such dependency by training programme in alternative livelihood.
- The government to providing a lot of development programme like, entrepreneurship.

Conclusion

The school system like many other socio-cultural systems behaves as though they are upper-caste spaces. In the minds of Dalits students, they remain someone else's spaces. As elaborated above, this sense of alienation is affirmed by the functioning of the school system and the attitudes of the various agents within it. Just as with other public sphere institutions, the school still remains a space they enter only with hesitation.

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